

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Case Study

Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate; A Novel Potassium-Binding Agent for Hyperkalemia in Advanced Chronic Kidney Disease: A First Use Case Report in India

Kushal Anand, Ranil Boopathi S, Manish Kumar Singla*

Max Super Specialty Hospital, Mohali, Punjab, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 04 May 2026

Keywords:

Sodium zirconium cyclosilicate; Resistant Hyperkalemia; Chronic kidney disease; Potassium binders; Dialysis

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20021567

ABSTRACT

Hyperkalemia is a electrolyte disturbance commonly seen in patients with chronic kidney disease stage 5 (CKD 5), in which severe elevations (>6.0 mEq/L) pose a significant risk of morbidity and mortality, often preventing any necessary surgical intervention due to the danger of life-threatening arrhythmias and hemodynamic instability. Older potassium-binding agents such as calcium polystyrene sulphonate are not very effective especially in advanced CKD patients, requiring alternative therapeutic approaches. Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate (SZC), a novel selective potassium binder using selective ion exchange of potassium for hydrogen and sodium in the gastrointestinal tract, was approved by the FDA in 2018 but was only recently launched in India in December 2025, making real-world clinical experience limited in the Indian setting. This case reports the first documented use of SZC in Indian clinical practice. We present a 76-year-old male with CKD stage 5 not on dialysis who presented with chronic subdural hematoma requiring urgent surgical intervention. The patient developed severe resistant hyperkalemia (potassium 6.06 mEq/L) despite optimal therapy with calcium gluconate, beta-agonists, and calcium polystyrene sulphonate, delaying necessary surgical intervention. The inefficacy of older agents could be attributed to reduced gastrointestinal transit time and impaired colonic bioavailability characteristic of advanced CKD. Following dialysis refusal by the patient, SZC was initiated as a last resort attempt, at 5 mg three times daily. Within 12 hours of administration, serum potassium decreased drastically from 6.06 mEq/L to 4.39 mEq/L (reduction of 1.67 mEq/L), exceeding typical trial efficacy rates and enabling timely surgical intervention. The rapid and effective potassium reduction with SZC allowed successful burr hole craniotomy for hematoma evacuation without any operative complications. The patient had attained adequate potassium control throughout the

***Corresponding Author:** Manish Kumar Singla

Address: Max Super Specialty Hospital, Mohali, Punjab, India

Email ✉: manishsingladoc@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

perioperative and postoperative periods, with no adverse effects observed. This case demonstrates the superior efficacy and selective mechanism of action of SZC compared to conventional potassium binders in CKD stage 5 patients with resistant hyperkalemia and particularly in those declining or lacking access to dialysis, potentially allowing for its recommendation in future guidelines in over conventional older potassium-binding agents.

INTRODUCTION

Hyperkalemia is a commonly seen electrolyte disturbance in patients with chronic kidney disease stage 5 (CKD 5), due to the altered ability of excreting potassium through urine [1]. The incidence of hyperkalemia in CKD 5 patients increases with declining glomerular filtration rate [2]. Supplementing this information is that severe hyperkalemia ($K^+ >6.0$ mEq/L) is extremely dangerous to the cardiovascular system, causing arrhythmias, conduction abnormalities and hemodynamic instability preventing the patient from surgery whether it's elective or emergency until the electrolyte abnormality corrects [1][3].

The general treatment of hyperkalemia includes calcium gluconate for cardio protection, insulin with dextrose, beta-agonists, and potassium binders such as sodium polystyrene sulphonate (Kayexalate) and calcium polystyrene sulphonate (K-Bind) [1][4]. However, these agents have different and fluctuating efficacies and may not always provide adequate potassium reduction in patients, particularly those with severe baseline elevations or resistant hyperkalemia [2][4].

Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate (SZC) sold under the brand name LOKELMA is a novel class of non-absorbed, selective potassium binder that selectively exchanges potassium for hydrogen and sodium in the gastrointestinal tract [5]. With the gathered extensive clinical trial data on this drug, it has shown to have rapid onset of potassium reduction within one hour of administration, with dose-dependent efficacy across varying severity levels of hyperkalemia [5][6]. Despite FDA

approval in 2018, Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate has had limited use in Indian clinical practice, as it was only officially launched in India in December 2025 [7].

We present a case of a 76-year-old male with CKD Stage 5 not on dialysis, who developed subdural hemorrhage after suffering a fall at home and needed surgical intervention. In attempts to correct hyperkalemia, all necessary standard protocol management was given to the patient, showing no effect, delaying the need for a necessary surgery, necessitating escalation to newly launched drug, SZC which lead to the desired reduction in potassium required with this agent allowing the patient for timely surgical intervention that was previously contraindicated due to the severe electrolyte imbalance.

CASE REPORT

We observed a 76-year-old male patient who presented to the Max Super Specialty Hospital, Mohali, Punjab with the history of a fall one month ago with head trauma and bleeding on the day of the fall. The patient had gone to a local hospital a 2 day after the fall, for which he was given with the necessary medications and discharged. Then, about 1 week prior to the current admission, the patient had developed fresh symptoms like forgetfulness and confusion, after which the patient's family went for a CT Head Scan which showed a chronic subdural hematoma with significant mass effect, after which the patient was referred and admitted for further surgical intervention. The patient's past medical history included a Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting (CABG) performed in 2013, along with comorbidities like hypertension, hypothyroidism and CKD for last one and half years (not on dialysis). The patient's regular medications prior to admission included Amlodipine 5 mg daily, Metoprolol XR 50 mg daily, and Atorvastatin 20 mg at night. Physical examination on the day of

admission showed; Blood Pressure- 135/80 mmHg, Pulse Rate- 74 beats /min, Respiratory Rate- 22/min, SPO₂- 98%, Temperature- 97.2°F. Upon admission the patient was planned for a burr hole craniotomy for hematoma evacuation. However, preoperative clearance for surgery was based upon achieving acceptable electrolyte stability, particularly normalized serum potassium levels (target <5.0 mEq/L). The laboratory reports of serum showed the following electrolyte levels; Sodium- 132 mEq/L, Potassium- 5.36 mEq/L, Chloride- 104 mEq/L and Urea 121 mg/dL and was started on pharmacotherapy of, Amlodipine 5mg, Cap. Tab. Metoprolol XR 25mg BD and Tab. Atorvastatin 20mg at Night.

On Day 2, the patients laboratory electrolyte serum values showed: Sodium- 136 mEq/L, Potassium 5.76 mEq/L, Chloride- 106 mEq/L and Urea- 137 mg/dL. Given the elevated potassium level, corrective therapeutic measures were initiated; Inj. Calcium gluconate 10 mL intravenously over 10 minutes, Neb. Asthalin (salbutamol), Calcium Polystyrene Sulphonate (K-Bind) 1 sachet in 15 mL lactulose twice daily, along with a strict K+-Free diet.

On Day 3, Despite continuation of K-Bind BD therapy combined with all other potassium-lowering measures, serum potassium paradoxically had escalated to 5.85 mEq/L on Day 3 and further to 6.06 mEq/L on Day 4, demonstrating the poor-response of calcium polystyrene sulphonate regimen under the patient's physiology. These highly elevated potassium levels made the patient unsuitable for surgical intervention, as hyperkalemia of this magnitude carried a substantial risk of intraoperative arrhythmias and hemodynamic compromise, delaying a necessary surgery.

The option of dialysis was available and presented to the patient and the caretakers but was refused due to beliefs that if the patient was started on dialysis for this treatment will be needed for all

future treatments, as the patient is a CKD 5 not on dialysis. Fortunately, on the last hopes despite having tried all possible potassium-lowering methods, one more attempt was available. SZC which was launched only a few days prior in the Indian market, was ordered by the physician to reduce and correct the serum potassium imbalance.

SZC was initiated to the patient at a dose of 5mg three times daily as an alternative. This represented one of the first uses of SZC not only in our institution but also in India, due to its very fresh release to the Indian market. Approximately 12 hours after the first dose and following administration of the second dose of SZC, repeat laboratory testing revealed a reduction in serum potassium from 6.06 mEq/L to 4.39 mEq/L, a decrement of 1.67 mEq/L within half a day. This rapid normalization of potassium allowed for the patient to proceed with the planned burr hole craniectomy. On Day 5, following a successful burr hole craniotomy for evacuation of the chronic subdural hematoma, the serum electrolyte panel showed potassium to be controlled at 4.71 mEq/L with sodium and chloride remaining within normal ranges (136 and 107 mEq/L, respectively).

The rapid and effective control of hyperkalemia with SZC allowed the healthcare team to perform surgical intervention in a timely manner that was delayed due to the electrolyte instability. The patient tolerated the procedure well without intraoperative complications related to hyperkalemia or electrolyte imbalances and following the surgery was kept under observation in the ICU for 1 more day and then shifted to a private room for post-op recovery.

On Day 6, the patient was recovering well without any new complaints, showing improvement, Although there was a slight increase in the serum potassium levels, it hadn't exceeded 5.0 mEq/L, showing the efficacy of SZC in maintaining potassium levels within a safe range, even in such

hemodynamically compromised patients at high risk of electrolyte fluctuations due to the advanced CKD. The prescription of Lokelma (SZC) which was written for the patient had been completed, in which the patient received 6 total doses of Lokelma 5mg TDS for 2 days. Resulting in the successful reduction of serum potassium from a highly elevated range to one that was safe allowed to proceed for the surgery which was required and

continued post-op Aswell. This trend in recovery from the surgery and subsequent decreases in serum potassium (4.47, 4.61, 4.0) continued for the remainder of the days (Day 7,8,9) respectively, the patient stayed in the hospital until the completion of the post-op care and other discharge criteria required.

TABLE 1: Serial electrolyte and serum urea panel demonstrating the progressive hyperkalemia in the patient despite on-going measure to decrease potassium level and response to LOKELMA.

Parameter	Sodium (mEq/L)	Potassium (mEq/L)	Chloride (mEq/L)	Calcium (mEq/L)	Serum Urea (mg/dL)
DAY 1	132	5.36	104	8.64	131
DAY 2	136	5.76	106	8.58	137
DAY 3	138	5.85	108	-	130
DAY 4 (Pre-LOKELMA)	137	6.06	110	8.54	126
DAY 4 (LOKELMA started)	-	4.39	-	-	-
DAY 5 (Ongoing LOKELMA treatment)	136	4.71	107	8.66	123
DAY 6 (Lokelma Stopped at Night)	136	4.99	104	8.67	118
DAY 7	133	4.47	100	8.44	119
DAY 8	132	4.61	100	7.94	121
DAY 9	133	4.00	101	8.01	118

DISCUSSION

This case represents one of the documented uses of SZC in Indian clinical practice for management of hyperkalemia since its launch to the public, as it isn't widely available across hospitals, the case report aims to document its first Real-World use. Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate is a non-absorbed, microporous, inorganic compound that

selectively binds to potassium ions in the gastrointestinal lumen through preferential ion exchange of potassium for hydrogen and sodium [5]. Unlike older potassium binders such as sodium or calcium polystyrene sulphonate, which follow non-selective ion exchange, Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate demonstrates a higher affinity for potassium, resulting in superior efficacy and reduced sodium/calcium loading

[5][6]. It reaches maximal efficacy within 24-48 hours but shows onset of action as early as one hour after administration [5]. In Phase 2/3 clinical trials, Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate 10 mg administered three times daily achieved a mean serum potassium reduction of 0.7 mEq/L over 48 hours in patients with baseline hyperkalemia [6]. In the present case, a dose of 5 mg TDS achieved reduction of 1.67 mEq/L within 12 hours exceeding the efficacy typically observed in published trials, but can also be attributed to other factors like strict diet control, Neb. Asthalin and as well as the patient's highly elevated baseline potassium (6.06 mEq/L), as clinical pharmacology data indicate that patients with higher baseline potassium concentrations demonstrate greater absolute and proportional reductions with SZC [5][6]. The inefficacy of Calcium Polystyrene Sulphonate (K-Bind) in this patient, despite optimal dosing, raises important questions regarding the efficacy of older potassium binders in advanced CKD patients. Multiple factors may contribute to reduced effectiveness of polystyrene sulphonates in CKD Stage 5, including: Reduced gastrointestinal transit time and reduced GI surface contact time resulting from uremic alterations in

motility [8]. Impaired colonic bioavailability due to altered microbiota composition in advanced CKD [8]. Ion selectivity limitations of non-selective polystyrene exchange resins in high-potassium environments [5]. Individual genetic variation in sulphonate resin efficacy [9]. The higher affinity of sodium zirconium cyclosilicate's potassium-binding capacity may have overcome these limitations, as evidenced by the rapid clinical response observed in this case. The hyperkalemia leading to delays in the surgical intervention carried a highly relevant risk regarding morbidity and mortality for the patient [1][3]. But, due to this ability to rapidly normalize serum potassium with SZC any such events were prevented.

In this case all options to reduce hyperkalemia had been exhausted before considering the use of SZC aside from one, known as Paritomer [10]. It is a sodium-free, non-absorbed cation-exchange polymer approved for the treatment of hyperkalemia, especially in patients with CKD, diabetes, heart failure, or those on RAAS inhibitors, but the limitations of this drug come in its high cost and the fact that it isn't currently available for use in India [11][12].

TABLE 2: Treatment options for correcting Hyperkalemia: Class, Mechanism, and Clinical Profile

Medication	Drug Class	MOA	ROA	Onset of Action	Typical Dose
Calcium gluconate	Membrane stabilizer	Antagonizes cardiac membrane effects of hyperkalemia; does not lower serum K⁺ , but stabilizes myocardium	IV	Immediate (1–3 min)	10 mL of 10% solution IV over 2–5 min
Regular insulin + dextrose	Hormone (intracellular K ⁺ shift)	Stimulates Na ⁺ /K ⁺ -ATPase → shifts K ⁺ into cells	IV	15–30 min	Insulin 10 units IV + 25 g dextrose

Short-acting β_2-agonist (Albuterol/Salbutamol)	β_2 -adrenergic agonist	Activates Na^+/K^+ -ATPase \rightarrow intracellular K^+ shift	Inhalation (neb)	~ 30 min	10–20 mg via nebulization
Loop diuretic (Furosemide)	Loop diuretic	Increases renal potassium excretion	IV / Oral	15–60 min	20–80 mg IV or oral
Sodium polystyrene sulfonate (SPS)	Cation-exchange resin	Exchanges Na^+ for K^+ in colon \rightarrow fecal K^+ elimination	Oral / Rectal	≥ 2 –6 h (variable, slow)	15–60 g oral or rectal
Patiromer	Non-absorbed K^+ binder	Exchanges Ca^{2+} for K^+ in colon \rightarrow reduces total body K^+	Oral	~ 7 h	8.4–25.2 g once daily
Sodium zirconium cyclosilicate (SZC)	Selective potassium binder	Selectively traps K^+ throughout GI tract in exchange for Na^+/H^+	Oral	1–2 h	Acute: 10 g TID \times 48 h; Maintenance: 5–10 g daily
Hemodialysis	Extracorporeal potassium removal	Direct removal of potassium from blood	Extracorporeal	Immediate	Based on dialysis prescription

During the treatment period with Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate, no adverse effects were observed in the patient, the drug was tolerated well without any gastrointestinal complaints, electrolyte imbalances beyond the desired potassium reduction, or other safety concerns. Similarly clinical trial data also reflected that Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate is generally well-tolerated, with the most common adverse events being edema and generalized fluid retention in 8–11% of patients receiving standard maintenance dose and hypokalemia in 4.1% of trial participants, however this can be mitigated through careful electrolyte monitoring [5].

The limitations of this case report is that it describes a single patient's response and therefore cannot be generalized to all CKD 5 patients with hyperkalemia. Randomized controlled trials

comparing Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate directly to calcium and sodium polystyrene sulfonates in Indian CKD populations would strengthen evidence for preference of newer agents in this setting. Although the desired response was achieved, the exact underlying mechanism which showed Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate's superiority of efficacy in this patient compared to K-Bind isn't exactly understood. Potential explanations include the selective ion exchange mechanism and patient-specific factors related to gastrointestinal physiology in advanced CKD. The use of newer potassium binders underlines an important step in the right direction for CKD-related complication management in India, where many patients decline or have limited access to dialysis [13].

As the global burden of CKD increases and renal replacement therapy access remains limited in developing nations, effective oral potassium-binding agents become essential tools for reducing hospitalizations [10]. This case supports the potential widespread use of Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate as an effective option within CKD treatment.

CONCLUSION

We present the first documented case of Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate use in Indian clinical practice, demonstrating rapid and effective reduction of treatment-resistant hyperkalemia in a CKD Stage 5 patient, who wasn't willing for dialysis, The agent's superior efficacy compared to the conventional potassium binder; K-Bind (calcium polystyrene sulfonate) in this case allowed for surgical intervention that would otherwise have been contraindicated due to the severe electrolyte imbalance in the patient, potentially causing life-threatening complications. This case highlights the potential widespread clinical use of SZC as an important therapeutic option for managing difficult-to-treat hyperkalemia in advanced CKD, particularly in patients who decline or lack access to dialysis.

ABBREVIATIONS:

CKD- Chronic Kidney Disease

SZC- Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate

RAAS- Renin Angiotensin-Aldosterone System

ICU- Intensive care unit

Tab.- Tablet

Cap.- Capsule

Neb.- Nebulizer

Inj.- Injection

BD- Twice a day

TDS- Thrice a day

Ethics Statement: The informed consent form was obtained from the patient for publishing his medical records.

Conflicts of Interest: All authors declared no conflicts of interest.

Funding: No funding source is available

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HOW TO CITE: Kushal Anand, Ranil Boopathi S, Manish Kumar Singla, Sodium Zirconium Cyclosilicate; A Novel Potassium-Binding Agent for Hyperkalemia in Advanced Chronic Kidney Disease: A First Use Case Report in India, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 5, 548-555, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20021567>

